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Pilot investigation of laser self-mixing interference image generation in laser powder bed fusion and its potential for in-process monitoring

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Abstract

Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) is one of the most suitable technologies for manufacturing parts with complex geometric shapes and is widely used in industrial production. However, due to its complex processing parameters, achieving high-stability, high-quality production is challenging. Defects such as reduced dimensional accuracy, shrinkage deformation, and high surface roughness are common during the manufacturing process, making the process in need of monitoring systems for detection and assistance. Most existing optical monitoring systems focus on the geometric dimensions and shape features of the melt pool or use optical cameras to observe the workpiece from the fixed position, which have certain limitations. Therefore, this study proposed an image generation system based on laser self-mixing interference, which obtains digital images of surface features by scanning the sample surface with the laser controlled by the high-speed galvanometer. The system, after calibration and benchtop testing, can stably collect and record data to generate bitmaps. The spatial and optical resolution of the system were evaluated through knife-edge testing and optical chart testing. Different shapes of 316L LPBF samples were selected to verify the imaging capability of the prototype. It was found that the images generated by the prototype could observe the geometric structure of the processing area, presenting surface textures with the roughness (Ra) at the 3.0-3.9 μm level. Furthermore, by adjusting the scanning area and line spacing, local magnification imaging can be achieved, allowing for a clear observation of local geometric features and surface defects. The experimental results indicate that the prototype has great application potential in the detection of LPBF samples and can be applied in the process monitoring of additive manufacturing processes.

Keywords: laser measurement; self-mixing interference; monitoring; laser powder bed fusion; additive manufacturing

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction of LPBF

Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) is one of the most widely used Additive Manufacturing (AM) technologies, utilizing a high-energy laser beam to selectively melt powdered metals or alloys layer by layer, producing metal parts based on the three-dimensional model data of the designed geometry [1]. After more than a decade of research, LPBF technology has matured in terms of processing techniques. It is capable of producing parts with complex geometric features and lightweight components and is widely used in the fields of medical devices, automotive manufacturing, aerospace, and energy [2].

1.2 Common defects of LPBF

Although LPBF technology has relatively mature manufacturing processes, high-quality and highly reproducible production remains challenging due to the complexity of numerous process parameters and the non-steady-state printing process [3]. Inappropriate scanning patterns or laser power can lead to various types of dimensional and geometric deviations during the production process [4]. Using the fixed laser power to process parts can easily lead to heat accumulation and excessive melting in parts with special geometric features [5]. In such cases, uneven cooling speeds and thermal gradients of the parts can lead to inconsistent microstructures, thereby reducing overall shape accuracy [6]. Additionally, uneven contraction between the top and bottom of the part due to changes in temperature gradients often leads to shrinkage deformation and warping [7]. These defects can damage the surface structure and dimensional accuracy of the parts, and further deterioration can lead to delamination, severely affecting the quality and stability of the process [8]. Meanwhile, excessive heat dissipation can lead to insufficient melting of some features, resulting in defects such as high surface roughness [9], balling [10], and lack of fusion [11]. Surface roughness is also related to the mechanical properties of the parts, and unstable roughness and surface characteristics can lead to reduced fatigue performance of the parts [12]. These geometric deformations and surface roughness that occur during the processing can reduce the mechanical properties of the final formed parts, making the monitoring of the LPBF process particularly important.

Fig.1 The common defects of the LPBF process.
 (a) High surface roughness [9]; (b) Balling [10]; (c) Lack of fusion [11].

1.3 Current monitoring techniques

To improve the control of the LPBF printing process, many research groups have developed and designed various monitoring systems. These monitoring systems primarily use sensors that capture and analyse different feedback characteristics during the processing, such as optical [13], thermal [14], acoustic [15], or other types of signals [16]. Among them, optical imaging methods have become one of the most popular process monitoring solutions due to their ease of use, ease of integration with current processing systems, and the ability to control the distance from the processing area [17]. Optical imaging systems can capture surface information of parts and the powder bed and the features during the processing. Yang et al. achieved local melt pool monitoring during the LPBF processing of superalloy Inconel 625 using a high-frame-rate camera [18]. The system they developed is capable of observing the melt pool and heat-affected zone, and employs statistical process control for data processing and analysis, enabling the detection of under-melting and over-melting defects. Similarly, Mazzoleni et al. opted for a spatially resolved sensor (CMOS camera) to collect melt pool information [19]. By detecting visible and infrared wavelengths, they were able to accurately capture the dynamic geometric changes of the melt pool. With sufficient spatial and temporal resolution, they monitored the melt pool size variations and periodic changes such as splash ejection in real time. Furthermore, Giulia et al. targeted the splash-related information during the LPBF process and used a high-speed camera for image acquisition [20]. Combining image segmentation and feature extraction, they developed a logistic regression model to analyse the correlation between different energy density conditions and splash-related features under different quality states. Similarly, Zhang et al. employed a vision system equipped with a high-speed camera for process image acquisition [21], extracting feature parameters such as melt pool, plume, and splash during the process. The data results were analysed with SVM and CNN models. The CNN model achieved an accuracy rate as high as 92.7% in recognizing the quality of the LPBF process. Fabio et al. developed an open LPBF system, combining a CMOS camera with six directional light sources, to study the sensitivity of in-situ measurement to different lighting conditions and laser scanning directions [22]. By comparing different image pre-processing and segmentation algorithms, they proposed an experimental procedure for size

measurement that relies on simple geometric features, achieving high measurement repeatability. Bin Zhang et al. designed a monitoring system based on digital fringe projection technology to measure the surface morphology of the powder bed during the manufacturing process [23]. This system is capable of measuring the flatness of the powder bed, surface texture, average height of the fusion area, surface feature length, and the position and size of splash droplets.

1.4 Limitation of current monitoring techniques

Existing optical monitoring systems primarily focus on the geometric imaging of the melt pool and measurement analysis based on optical cameras. However, these systems have certain limitations. The analysis of the melt pool geometric dimensions and characteristic morphology is the indirect measurement, predicting the fusion state and print quality of the processed part through size, temperature distribution, and shape change behaviour [24]. They do not directly measure the surface features and geometric dimensions of the solidified part. Optical camera-based monitoring systems observe the processing area through a viewing window, and the field of view (FOV) captured in the images may include areas outside the processing area that are irrelevant to monitoring [25]. Moreover, if the installation position of the camera does not ensure the orthogonal projection onto the processing area, trapezoidal distortion will occur [26]. Images obtained from non-orthogonal projections will exhibit shape distortion, making it difficult to obtain accurate geometric features. These issues can hinder the effective monitoring of the LPBF process.

1.5 Proposed laser self-mixing scanning imaging technique

This paper proposes a scanning imaging system based on laser self-mixing interference for observing the surface topography and geometric features of LPBF-processed samples. The design of this system is inspired by the scanning electron microscope (SEM). Although the physical and imaging mechanisms are different, the same scanning imaging principle can be applied. As shown in Fig. 2, the imaging principle of the SEM is based on electrons being accelerated and then striking a conductive specimen surface to generate secondary electrons (SE) and backscattered electrons (BSE). After SE and BSE are captured by an electron sensor and converted into electrical signals, then the signals will be amplified and used to create a simulated fluorescent image on a cathode ray tube [27]. The system introduced in this study uses a laser beam generated by a diode that, under the control of a galvanometer mirror, illuminates the measurement target surface. The reflected laser beam returns to the diode and undergoes self-mixing with the original laser beam, which will be collected by a built-in photodiode and converted into an electrical signal. The feedback laser signal, after conversion and processing, will be used for imaging.

Compared to traditional optical imaging systems, the imaging results of this system are generated rather than captured, thus will be able to avoid trapezoidal distortion. Raster-scanning will be conducted via a set of high-speed galvanometer (galvo) scanners, instead of relying on the slow recoater movement as in the case of the line-scan profilometer. Additionally, the system allows to change the field of view and magnification by simply adjusting the scan line spacing and scanning area, enabling precise acquisition of feature information from the processing area and reducing the proportion of useless data. The imaging method proposed in this paper addresses the limitations of existing monitoring methods to some extent, and to the

best of our knowledge, this study is the first to apply the self-mixing phenomenon as an imaging technique for the monitoring of an additive manufacturing process.

Fig. 2 The same scanning imaging principle as SEM can be applied to the prototype

2 Material and Methods

This section introduces the principle and design of laser self-mixing imaging, signal processing electronics and image generation software, and the above parts were developed to build a prototype of the LPBF scanning imaging system. The prototype was initially tested and its imaging capability was verified. On this basis, the experimental device and experimental design for studying the spatial resolution of the prototype were designed. Then, the parts processed by LPBF were scanned to generate digital images.

2.1 Laser diode self-mixing imaging system design

The study employed laser self-mixing interferometry as its core imaging method. The operational mechanism of the measurement apparatus is delineated in Fig. 3. Fig. 3(a) presents the detailed schematic of the internal architecture of a semiconductor laser diode and its operational diagram. This setup comprises a laser diode integrated with a photodiode. Upon energization, the photodiode initiates a probing laser beam, which is directed towards the target's surface via a compound lens. After interaction with the target, which includes absorption and reflection, the portion of the probing laser beam laden with surface characteristics, retraces its path back to the diode cavity. The resultant feedback laser beam arises from the self-interference phenomenon between the emitted laser from the diode and the reflected beam. This feedback laser undergoes self-mixing interferometry, where the amplitude and frequency perturbations caused by the interference are transduced into an electrical signal variation by the photodiode. Subsequently, these variations are processed through dedicated circuits and algorithms to ascertain the dimensions and surface texture of the measurement target.

Fig. 3(b) elucidates an analogous Fabry-Perot cavity model [28], which accounts for the self-mixing interference of the laser. Eq. 1 delineates the phase shift of the laser due to the self-

mixing of the reflected laser light. Eq. 2 articulates the alterations in laser power and frequency after self-mixing [29].

$$r = E_r/E_i \quad r_{eff} = r_2 + r_2 \xi e^{(-2\pi\nu_F \tau_D)} \quad (1)$$

$$P(t) = E^2(t) \quad P(t) = P_0(1 + m \cos(2\pi\nu_F \tau_D)) \quad (2)$$

where r is the reflection coefficient; E_r and E_i are the electric fields of the reflected and incident laser light; r_{eff} is the equivalent mirror reflection coefficient; ξ is the coupling factor between the target and the laser cavity; $P(t)$ and P_0 are the optical output power with and without feedback; m is the feedback parameters coefficient; ν_F is the lasing frequency under feedback; τ_D is the travelling time of the laser light outside of its diode cavity.

Fig. 3 (a) Laser measurement module setup;
 (b) Fabry-Perot cavity and equivalent model [28].

Fig. 4 (a) and (b) provide the schematic diagram of the design of the laser diode self-mixing imaging system. The prototype mainly included the laser diode module, laser collimator, beam expander, focusing lens, and galvo scanner. The laser diode (with built-in photodiode) was installed in the heat sink, and the power source circuit was used to provide a stable operating voltage and current. The movable collimator lens and focusing lens combination were used to adjust the laser spot size. The Galvo drive circuit was controlled by a microcontroller, which can adjust the scanning speed and scanning area.

Fig. 4 (a) Design of laser diode self-mixing imaging system;
 (b) Laser diode self-mixing imaging system prototype.

2.2 Signal processing electronics design

The signal-processing electronic device consisted of a signal amplifier and a data logger. As shown in Fig. 5, the signal amplifier processed the feedback current signal from the photodiode by performing conversion, noise reduction, and amplification, outputting a feedback voltage signal with the enhanced signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). This output signal was transmitted to the data logger for further processing, temporarily stored in the data logger's internal memory, and then transferred to a computer via a universal serial bus (USB) port.

Fig. 5 Block diagram of the signal amplifier.

Fig. 6 illustrates the operation flow of the data logger. Each scan line starting during the laser raster scan corresponds to the beginning of each data acquisition cycle. This design ensures the

accuracy of data acquisition. Consequently, the scanning signals for the X and Y axes, which control the laser scan, are also input into the data logger for reference. Fig. 7(a) provides an example of the X and Y scanning signals controlling the galvo during the laser raster scan. Fig. 7(b) shows the corresponding raster scan schematic.

Fig. 6. Data logger process flow chart.

Fig. 7. (a) Typical raster scan signal on a 2D Cartesian plane, the X scanning signal is a sawtooth waveform guiding the laser beam from left to right, while the Y signal uses step increments to deflect the beam to a new scan line. (b) The resulting raster scan pattern consists of multiple scan lines.

2.3 Image generation software

After processing by the signal amplifier and data logger, the feedback voltage signal data was transmitted to a monitoring computer, where Python programming generated digital images. Fig. 8 illustrates the workflow of the image generation software. The data transferred from the data logger was sliced and converted into individual integer data points after being identified and determined by the software. Then, these converted data points were reassigned to the corresponding row and column positions to form a digital matrix, which was used to generate a grayscale bitmap and stored in a digital image format. The software design allows for the

customization of various parameters, such as image pixel size, image bit depth, image format, and file name.

Fig. 8. Image generation software process flow chart.

2.4 Spatial resolution analysis

Spatial resolution is one of the most critical characteristics of an optical imaging system, as it determines the system's ability to discern surface details of the target specimen [30]. Concurrently, the shape and dimensions of a laser beam can serve as criteria for evaluating the resolution of a laser imaging system, with spatial resolution being constrained by the size of the imaging laser beam [31]. Therefore, in this study, the measurement of the laser beam dimensions was adopted as a standard for assessing the spatial resolution of the imaging system. According to existing research, there are various established techniques for characterizing Gaussian laser beams, including the slit scan technique, the pinhole technique, and the knife-edge technique. Data analysis and calculation methods encompass Full Width Half Maximum (FWHM) [32], $1/e^2$ width [33], $D4\sigma$ width (second-moment width) [34], and knife edge width [35,36], among others.

In this paper, the knife-edge technique, which is most commonly used and offers rapid analysis with a simple experimental setup yet yields accurate results, was selected to measure the spatial resolution of the laser imaging system. Employing this technique, when the laser beam is moved perpendicularly to the knife-edge (as indicated by the red dashed lines in Fig. 9(a)) and passes through a sharp edge, the spatial distribution profile of the beam intensity, known as the Edge Spread Function (ESF), can be observed in Fig. 9(b). The distance between the knife-edge positions corresponding to 10% and 90% of the maximum beam intensity provides the beam diameter value for an ideal Gaussian beam, which is indicative of the spatial resolution of the imaging system.

Fig. 9. Sharp edge and the definition of spatial resolution from an ESF.

(a) TEM grid with 40µm hole (adapted to show scan direction).

(b) Resolution is the spatial width of values 10% to 90% of maximum value [35].

2.5 Experimental setup

The laser imaging system for the LPBF process proposed in this paper was composed of a laser diode scanning imaging system, signal processing electronics, and image generation software. Consequently, four sets of digital image generation experiments were designed to validate the imaging capabilities of the system. The first set of experiments aimed to verify the prototype's digital acquisition and image generation capabilities. The second set of experiments was

conducted to test the spatial resolution of the imaging system. The third and fourth sets of experiments validated the prototype's ability to generate digital images for LPBF samples.

2.5.1 Analog signal imaging experiment

In the first set of experiments, the virtual voltage signals generated by the microcontroller were used to verify the data acquisition and image generation capabilities of the prototype. Unlike the actual self-mixing imaging process, the laser scanning system was not directly connected. However, the software and hardware for data acquisition and image generation were operated under real conditions. During the testing, the custom-developed waveform generation module produced virtual X & Y direction scanning signals and virtual feedback voltage signals to simulate the laser scanning imaging process. The virtual feedback signals were captured and transmitted to the prototype to generate digital images. Fig. 10(a) and (b) illustrate the workflow and signal generation principles of the waveform generation.

Fig. 10. (a) Block diagram of the waveform generator.

(b) Waveform generation working flow chart.

Fig. 11 presents the configuration of the virtual voltage signals used for testing, where the first two virtual signals simulate the voltage inputs controlling the Galvo for the raster scanning pattern. The virtual X-direction scanning signal was in sawtooth waveform to control the horizontal movement of the laser. The virtual Y-direction scanning signal was in step waveform to control laser moving to the next line after completing each scan line. The virtual feedback voltage signal was assigned three voltage levels to generate digital image with three equally wide stripes, each stripe with different grayscale values. The virtual signals simulated by the waveform generation can validate the capabilities of the prototype before the LPBF experiment through the successful reconstruction of the stripe image waveforms. Table 1 provides the benchtop test settings in virtual signal simulations and waveform reconstruction.

Fig. 11. The signals generated by the waveform generation.

Table 1. Benchtop test settings.

Benchtop Test Parameter	Value
Virtual feedback voltage signal level	1.0 V, 2.0 V, 3.0 V
Virtual X & Y scanning signal frequency	100 Hz
Data logger sampling frequency	120 kHz
Data logger input/output range	0 to 3.3 V
Imaging size (row \times column)	1200 pixels \times 1200 pixels
Image bit depth	8 bits, 256

2.5.2 Spatial resolution experiment

The second set of experiments was conducted using the knife-edge test to measure the spatial resolution of the prototype. The experiment utilized the complete laser scanning system, signal amplifier, data logger, and digital image generation software. In the experiment, the laser beam size was evaluated as an indicator of spatial resolution. As shown in Fig. 12, the plate specimen with a black-and-white halftone pattern was designed as the imaging target for the test. The use of black and white to create a colour contrast is because the feedback laser signal is highly sensitive to the reflectivity and absorptivity of the material and colour. When the laser beam scans perpendicularly to the black-white edge, the edge of the colour transition can be used to assess the size of the laser beam. Additionally, considering that the shape of the laser spot will affect the beam size measurement, the spatial resolution was scanned and evaluated separately in the X and Y directions (as shown in Fig. 12(a)). After generating the original digital images, pixel value distributions from five scan lines (pixel row indices: 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000) were extracted from each image for spatial resolution analysis. According to the data calculation

method given in Fig. 9(b), the pixel value distribution was analysed to determine the spatial resolution of the laser imaging system prototype.

Fig. 12. (a) Laser scan path of the X/Y direction spatial resolution measurement.
(b) Imaging target of the spatial resolution experiment.

2.5.3 LPBF components imaging experiment

In the third set of experiments, the prototype performed laser scanning imaging tests on 316L LPBF samples at room temperature. The samples were processed by an LPBF machine using 316L stainless steel powder with the size range of 15-53 microns. Fig. 13 shows the specimens designed for the test. These samples, in common basic shapes, were developed as standard laser imaging test versions. They were intended to study the pixel value image contrast between sintered powder and solidified surfaces.

Building on the third set of experiments, the fourth set aimed to generate images with the certain magnification. The same samples were locally magnified and imaged to study imaging zoom-in capability of the prototype. Table 2 and Table 3 outline the processing parameters for the LPBF samples and the imaging configurations of the prototype in the third and fourth sets of experiments.

Fig. 13. The completed test specimens manufactured by the LPBF machine with 316L powder.

Table 2. LPBF specimens processing configuration.

Processing Parameter	Value
Particle size distribution	15-53 μm (316L)
Processing laser power	350 W
Processing laser wavelength	1070 nm
Processing laser beam size	50 μm
Processing laser scanning speed	600 mms^{-1}
Thickness of powder layer	0.6 mm

Table 3. Laser imaging system prototype configuration.

Prototype Parameter	Value
X & Y scanning signal frequency	100 Hz
Data logger sampling frequency	120 kHz
Data logger input/output range	0 to 3.3 V
Imaging size (row \times column)	1200 pixels \times 1200 pixels
Image bit depth	8 bits, 256
Imaging area (W \times D)	60 mm \times 60 mm, 20 mm \times 20 mm
Working distance	200 mm
Laser wavelength	639 nm
Laser power	210 mW
Laser beam size	213.7 μm (D4 σ X), 300.2 μm (D4 σ Y)
Laser speed	6 ms ⁻¹

3 Results

This section presents the results of system prototype capability verification, spatial resolution evaluation, and digital image generation of LPBF specimens.

3.1 System capability verifications

The benchtop test was conducted to verify the digital image generation capability of the prototype. Based on the simulated virtual feedback signals, a three-stripe bitmap was reconstructed. Fig. 14(a) displays a typical waveform diagram of the X & Y scanning signals and the virtual feedback signals. Fig. 14(b) presents the reconstructed image results, generating a pattern with three stripes of different pixel values, where the average pixel value of each stripe in the reconstructed grayscale bitmap is defined by Eq. 3.

$$P_i = \frac{V_{DLi}}{V_{DLMAX}} \times N \quad (3)$$

where P_i is average pixel value. $i=1, 2, 3$, representing the three stripes. V_{DLi} is average sampled pixel voltage (from feedback electron) received at the data logger. $i=1, 2, 3$, representing the three voltages of the three-stripe region. V_{DLMAX} is the maximum input voltage of the data logger, which is +3.3V for the test. N is grayscale bit depth of an image, $N=256$, 8-bit, in the case of the benchtop test.

Fig. 14. (a) A friction of the X/Y scanning signal and the virtual feedback signal generated by the waveform generator. (b) 1200 pixels \times 1200 pixels (row \times column) digital image with three equidistant stripes.

The bitmap generation software, after capturing the virtual feedback signals, produced images consisting of 1200 pixels per pixel row, i.e., one waveform. From the result dataset, 20 waveforms and 24,000 sampling points of virtual feedback voltage signal data were randomly

selected to analyse the accuracy of the data logger signal levels and data acquisition periods. The mean (μ), standard deviation (σ), and coefficient of variation (C_v) of the signal data point pixel values were calculated, and the number of pixels allocated to each of the three stripe regions in the reconstructed image was statistically analysed. Tables 4 and 5 give the results of the analyses.

According to the data in Table 4, the difference between the average pixel values in the three stripe regions and the theoretical values is less than 2%, and the C_v values caused by the fluctuation of pixel values within each stripe region are all less than 0.26%. The results in Table 5 indicate that there were no variations in the number of pixels allocated to the three stripe regions for the sampled waveforms, and the difference between the average number of pixels in each part of the scanning line and the theoretical value is less than 2%.

Table 4. Average pixel values of the three-stripe region.

Parameter	Theoretical Pixel Value	μ	σ	C_v (%)
L1	38.636	39.000	0.101	0.259
L2	100.455	101.995	0.140	0.137
L3	154.545	157.005	0.405	0.258

Table 5. Average number of pixels in each section of the three-stripe region.

Parameter	Theoretical Number of Pixel	μ	σ	C_v (%)
Stripe 1	400	393	0.000	0.000
Stripe 2	400	405	0.000	0.000
Stripe 3	400	402	0.000	0.000

3.2 Spatial resolution analysis

In the spatial resolution assessment experiments, five original digital images were generated for each direction setting (X and Y directions). Fig. 15(a) displays a typical original bitmap, from which five scan lines were extracted for knife-edge resolution calculation. Fig. 15(b) shows the typical pixel value ESF extracted from the original image and the spatial resolution definition based on the criteria given in Fig. 9(b). The pixel value data from the original digital images were best fitted using linear regression [31] and a modified standard hyperbolic tangent function, $\tanh(x)$, as shown in Eq. (4). The image spatial resolution was calculated based on Eq. (5).

$$P(x) = P_0 + \alpha \tanh\left(\frac{x-x_0}{\beta}\right) \quad (4)$$

where $P(x)$ is the pixel value of the selected scan line (pixel row), x is the pixel column index of the selected scan line. P_0 , α , x_0 and β are parameters used to modify the standard $\tanh(x)$ function: P_0 controls the offset in pixel value, α controls the amplification in magnitude, x_0 controls the offset in pixel column index, and β controls the spread of the function.

$$P_{sp} = \Delta Img_{Col} \times \frac{Img_{width,mm}}{Img_{width,pixel}} \quad (5)$$

where P_{sp} (mm) is the pixel value, ΔImg_{Col} (pixel) is the number of pixels between two-pixel columns with 10% and 90% of the maximum pixel values, $Img_{width, mm}$ (mm) and $Img_{width, pixel}$ is the digital image 2D size (60 mm and 1200 pixels).

Fig. 15. Spatial resolution experimental result analysis. (a) Five scan lines for spatial resolution analysis. (b) Scan line pixel value ESF and the spatial resolution width.

Tables 6 and 7 present the spatial resolution assessment results for the measurement directions of X direction and Y direction. The data indicate that the calculated spatial resolution in the X direction ranges from 0.193 to 0.218 mm, while in the Y direction, it ranges from 0.274 to 0.311 mm, with the standard error being below 4%.

Table. 6 Spatial resolution result (X direction).

Laser Image Sample Number	R_{sp} (mm)	Standard Error
1	0.218	0.0214
2	0.193	0.0195
3	0.194	0.0226
4	0.220	0.0286
5	0.198	0.0199

Table. 7 Spatial resolution result (Y direction).

Laser Image Sample Number	R _{sp} (mm)	Standard Error
1	0.296	0.0273
2	0.274	0.0186
3	0.300	0.0197
4	0.311	0.0256
5	0.289	0.0312

To further assess the resolution of the prototype, an optical resolution test was added. The experiment utilized the 1951 USAF resolution test chart, which is widely used to test the resolving power of optical imaging systems such as microscopes and cameras, as the imaging target, as shown in Fig. 16(a). The imaging results of the resolution test chart pattern by the imaging system determine its resolution limit, where the smallest line group that cannot be resolved by the imaging system is its resolution limit, and the resolution can be calculated using Eq. 6 and Eq. 7. Fig. 16(b) displays the imaging results of the prototype, from which it can be analysed that its resolution limit is the first group, second element, corresponding to a resolution of 2.245 lp/mm (222.72 μm).

$$Resolution \text{ (Line pairs/mm)} = 2^{\left(\text{Group Number} + \frac{\text{Element Number} - 1}{6}\right)} \quad (6)$$

$$Resolution \text{ (}\mu\text{m)} = \frac{500}{2^{\left(\text{Group Number} + \frac{\text{Element Number} - 1}{6}\right)}} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 16. Optical resolution experiment result analysis. (a) USAF 1951 resolution test target. (b) Resolution test target imaging result.

3.3 Digital imaging generation of LPBF parts

After determining the spatial resolution of the prototype, imaging tests were conducted on components processed by LPBF. Prior to the imaging trials, the dimensional benchmark test of the prototype was assessed using the dimension standard part (GB/T) made of stainless steel. Fig. 17(a) presents the dimensional standard part used in the experiment, with a width of 300

mm (X-direction dimension) that can be used to calibrate the size accuracy of the prototype imaging results. Fig. 17(b) shows the imaging results of the target, from which scan lines at five positions were extracted for dimensional analysis. The pixel points of the selected scan lines from the original bitmap were extracted, and the geometric dimensions of the imaging samples were calculated based on the differences in pixel value data using Eq. 8. Table 6 provides the measurement results of the standard parts, and the data indicate that the error rate in dimensional measurement is below 1%.

$$L_i = \frac{Pn_i}{Pn_{per\ line}} \times L_{imgwidth} \quad (8)$$

where L_i is the target dimension, Pn_i is the pixel number of targets, $Pn_{per\ line}$ is the pixel number per scan line, and $L_{imgwidth}$ is the dimension of the laser scanning area.

Fig. 17. Dimension accuracy experiment result analysis.
(a) 300 mm standard part. (b) Five scan lines for dimension accuracy analysis.

Table. 6 Benchmark dimensions experimental results.

Parameter	Theoretical Number of Pixel	Actual Number of Pixel	Measured Dimension	Error (%)
P1	600	602	30.10	0.33
P2	600	604	30.20	0.67
P3	600	605	30.25	0.83
P4	600	603	30.15	0.50
P5	600	604	30.20	0.67
Average		603.60	30.18	0.60

The prototype conducted imaging trials on LPBF components under room temperature and typical lighting conditions. During the imaging process, the software detects and records the system control voltage signals and feedback signals to assist in analysis and troubleshooting. The feedback voltage signals were passed through the median filter to eliminate noise in the

images after collection. The data transmitted to the bitmap generation software, histogram equalization was used to enhance the image contrast. Fig. 18 displays the digital images generated by the laser imaging system prototype and the LPBF samples used in the tests. The prototype was capable of distinguishing between metal powder and sintered areas and accurately reconstructing the geometric features of the samples.

Furthermore, to assess the imaging stability of the system, imaging trials were conducted on components under different lighting conditions as shown in Fig.19 (i.e., light pollution). And Fig. 20 presents the imaging results in the dark environment, the high-intensity flashing light environment, and the typical light environment, with no significant differences observed in the comparative results.

Fig. 18. LPBF imaging experiment results. (a) - (d) LPBF components for imaging test. (e) - (h) 1200 pixels \times 1200 pixels digital images of the LPBF components covering imaging area of 60 mm \times 60 mm.

Fig. 19. Light pollution imaging experimental setup. (a) Dark. (b) Flashing light. (c) General light.

Fig. 20. Light pollution imaging experimental results. (a) Dark. (b) Flashing light.
(c) General light.

3.4 Magnification digital imaging generation of LPBF parts

The magnification imaging experiments were conducted using LPBF samples with letter patterns as the target. The scanning position and imaging area can be altered by adjusting the voltage signals controlling the galvo. The imaging area for the magnification imaging experiment was set to $20\text{ mm} \times 20\text{ mm}$, with the digital image size maintained at $1200\text{ pixels} \times 1200\text{ pixels}$. Fig. 18 displays the comparison between the imaging results and the actual photographs of the test samples. After observing the feature loss and geometric deformation in the letter "K" and letter "O" regions in Fig. 21 (a) with the imaging area of $60\text{ mm} \times 60\text{ mm}$, magnification imaging (zoom in to $20\text{ mm} \times 20\text{ mm}$) was performed on these two regions. Fig. 21 (b) reveals noticeable surface defects on the letter "K," while Fig. 21 (c) demonstrates the letter "O" with processing deformation.

Fig. 21. Local magnification imaging experiment results. (a) 1200 pixels \times 1200 pixels digital images covering imaging area of 60 mm \times 60 mm – area 1. (b) 1200 pixels \times 1200 pixels digital images covering imaging area of 20 mm \times 20 mm – area 2. (c) 1200 pixels \times 1200 pixels digital images covering imaging area of 20 mm \times 20 mm – area 3. (d) LPBF letter pattern component.

Additionally, another local imaging experiment (20 mm \times 20 mm, 1200 pixels \times 1200 pixels) was conducted on an LPBF lattice structure component made of 316L powder. The geometric feature dimensions of the LPBF lattice structure component were measured using an optical microscope (HiROX, MXB-10C), with the width of the mesh section being approximately 173.39 μm , as shown in Fig. 22(c). Comparing the imaging results shown in Fig. 22(b) with the actual object in Fig. 22(a), the wavy mesh pattern on the sample surface can be observed. Moreover, the imaging results accurately reproduce the shape differences caused by processing defects in position 1 and position 2.

Fig. 22. Local magnification imaging experiment results. (a) LPBF lattice structure component. (b) 1200 pixels \times 1200 pixels digital images covering imaging area of 20 mm \times 20 mm. (c) Microstructure dimension of lattice structure component.

4 Discussions

4.1 System capability verifications

The benchtop test was conducted to verify the data acquisition capability and digital image generation capability of the prototype. The image generation software produced the 1200 pixels \times 1200 pixels (row \times column) bitmap through the virtual feedback voltage signal from waveform generation. Additionally, the analysis of 20 waveforms and 24,000 sampled virtual feedback signal data points indicated that the average pixel value in the three stripe regions differed from their theoretical values by less than 2%, with the coefficient of variation Cv values for the dataset less than 0.26% (Table 4). This proves that the data logger is capable of capturing the virtual feedback signals and reconstructing the three grayscales of the image with the aforementioned precision. Furthermore, the error rates of the pixel number in the three stripe regions are less than 2% compared to theoretical values, with Cv values are 0. These results indicate that the data acquisition from the virtual feedback signals can be performed stably, thereby producing reconstructed images with three equally spaced stripes with the aforementioned precision. It can be concluded that the imaging capabilities of the prototype have been validated through the reconstruction of three-stripe images with sufficient sampling accuracy in both time and numerical values.

4.2 Spatial resolution analysis

Referring to the data in Tables 6 and 7, the average spatial resolution assessments for the X and Y directions were 0.2046 mm and 0.294 mm which were summarised in Fig. 23(a). Considering that the spatial resolution of the imaging system is related to the laser beam size,

the laser spot size measured by the charge-coupled device (CCD) was as a benchmark, as shown in Fig. 23(b). Compared to the CCD measurement results of 0.2137 mm ($D4\sigma_X$) and 0.3002 mm ($D4\sigma_Y$) in Fig. 23(b), the spatial resolution obtained by the knife-edge measurement method had errors of 4.26% and 2.07%. Additionally, compared to the optical resolution of 222.72 μm measured by the 1951 USAF resolution test chart, these values are of the same order of magnitude. This validates the effectiveness of the experimental setup and data analysis methods. The analysis results indicate that the bottleneck of spatial resolution in this study lies with the size of the prototype laser beam.

Fig. 23 Edge spatial resolution result analysis.

(a) Spatial resolution results. (b) Benchmark beam size measurement by CCD.

4.3 Digital imaging generation of LPBF parts

The design of laser scanning imaging experiments was undertaken to explore the potential for monitoring the LPBF process through laser imaging. During the imaging trials, digital images of LPBF components were generated. As shown in Fig. 18, the produced bitmaps achieved the desired user-defined size and bit depth. The images exhibit the contrast between the solidified 316L part surface areas and the unmelted metal powder. It can be inferred that the darker regions (lower pixel values) in Fig. 18(e)-(f) correspond to the unmelted 316L metal powder, while the lighter regions represent the processed solidified metal surfaces. Qualitatively, the solidified metal surfaces, compared to the metal powder, have a higher reflectivity to the detection laser, with more reflected laser returning to the laser diode module. The metal powder areas result in higher feedback voltage signal values, leading to higher pixel values. After the raw data is processed with a median filter to reduce noise and histogram equalization to enhance image contrast, the geometric features of differently shaped test samples can be clearly presented.

Additionally, the texture of the metal surface and the traces formed on the processed surface after laser processing and pool solidification can be discerned from the digital images. The typical metal sample surfaces were characterized using an optical microscope, and their surface roughness was measured, yielding the results shown in Fig. 24 and Table 7. The profile method

was used to measure the roughness of the components, and in order to ensure the universality of the measurement results, the measurement results at five different locations were obtained. The maximum height difference (Rz) of the sample surfaces is 13-18.3 μm , and the ten-point mean roughness (Rzjis) ranges from 8.2 to 12.7 μm . This indicates the ability to discern surface textures with height differences of several micrometres from the data images. Furthermore, the surface roughness data measured by arithmetic mean deviation (Ra) of 3.0-3.9 μm confirms that the prototype imaging results can recognize surface roughness at the micrometre level to a certain extent.

Fig. 24 The surface texture of typical LPBF component.

Table 7. The roughness of typical LPBF component.

Name	Roughness Ra (μm)	Roughness Rz (μm)	Roughness Rzjis (μm)
Profile 1	3.8	17.5	9.4
Profile 2	3.9	18.3	9.8
Profile 3	3.8	14.4	10.9
Profile 4	3.5	13.0	12.7
Profile 5	3.0	14.1	8.2

4.4 Magnification digital imaging generation of LPBF parts

The prototype is capable of adjusting the scanning position and magnification to generate test images according to actual imaging requirements, as shown in Fig. 21(a)-(c). Data calculated and presented in Table 8 indicate that when the imaging area is 60 mm \times 60 mm of the entire sample, the image magnification is 5.627, and when the imaging area is 20 mm \times 20 mm, the achievable magnification is 16.881. Observations from the imaging results reveal anomalies in the letter "K" region and the letter "O" in Fig. 21(a), including feature loss and geometric deformation. Upon magnified imaging, it was found that the letter "O" exhibited severe processing deformation. Characterization and measurement of the letter "K" region yielded the

results shown in Fig. 25 and Table 9. The maximum height difference (Rz) of this area's surface is 23.5-30.3 μm , the ten-point mean roughness (Rzjis) ranges from 15.5 to 20.6 μm , and the surface roughness measured by arithmetic mean deviation (Ra) is 4.4-6.0 μm . Comparison with the results obtained in Table 7 indicates that the letter "K" region has higher surface roughness with noticeable surface defects, which corresponds to the phenomena observed in the imaging results. Magnified imaging more clearly reveals dimensional errors and surface roughness as processing defects. The ability to achieve user-defined image magnification demonstrates the prototype's potential to zoom in on specific regions of an image, which, when fully integrated with the LPBF machine, can display local component features or defects.

Table 8. The magnifications were calculated for images covering different imaging areas based on 1920 pixel / 540.20mm computer monitoring.

Monitoring area (mm ²)	Image size (pixel ²)	Image size (mm ²)	Magnification
60 × 60	1200 × 1200	337.625 × 337.625	5.627
20 × 20	1200 × 1200	337.625 × 337.625	16.881

Fig. 25 The surface texture of the LPBF component.

Table 9. The roughness of typical LPBF component.

Name	Roughness Ra (μm)	Roughness Rz (μm)	Roughness Rzjis (μm)
Profile 1	5.7	26.8	15.5
Profile 2	5.8	26.7	16.6
Profile 3	5.5	25.2	17.8
Profile 4	4.4	23.5	12.8
Profile 5	6.0	30.3	20.6

5 Conclusion

This paper introduces a scanning imaging system based on laser self-mixing interference. Although the prototype in this study was only used to test LPBF 316L components, it is believed that the design process and technical details described can provide a reference for readers who want to carry out similar work on other AM machines.

The imaging performance of the prototype was validated through benchtop testing and spatial resolution analysis. Analysis of the data results from the benchtop test indicated that the prototype had pixel value counts and numerical errors below 2%, proving the stable data acquisition capability and accurate voltage-to-pixel value conversion ability of the prototype. Additionally, the spatial resolution of the prototype was assessed using the knife-edge test method, and the optical resolution was evaluated using the 1951 USAF resolution test chart. The average spatial resolution measured in the X and Y directions was 0.2046 mm and 0.294 mm, with the optical resolution was 0.223 mm (222.72 μm). Compared to the actual measurements of 0.2137 mm ($D4\sigma_X$) and 0.3002 mm ($D4\sigma_Y$), these values are of the same order of magnitude. This confirms the effectiveness of the experimental setup and data analysis methods.

Laser scanning imaging tests were conducted on 316L components processed by the LPBF process, and digital images were generated by the prototype. The distinction between metal powder and processed metal surfaces could be determined based on different grayscale values in the imaging results, and the geometric features of the processing area could be observed in the bitmaps. Moreover, the digital images were able to present surface textures with a roughness (R_a) at the 3.0-3.9 μm level. Additionally, the prototype provided the ability to adjust the region of the image and magnification according to user-defined settings, with a magnification of 16.881 (imaging area of 20 mm \times 20 mm). Furthermore, by magnifying local features, local geometric features and surface defects could be clearly observed.

Regarding imaging and data collection for LPBF processing, it can be considered that the laser scanning imaging system has the potential to become an alternative to thermal imaging and structured light imaging systems. The greatest challenge to realizing this application potential is to achieve in-process scanning imaging. These challenges mainly include achieving multi-layer original imaging during the additive manufacturing process, operating stably in high-temperature processing environments, and dealing with splashes caused by high-energy lasers evaporating metal powder. If these functionalities can be realized, it would be possible to identify defects and inspect and analyse the quality of fusion during the manufacturing process. This would lead to the effective manufacturing of certified metal parts for safety-critical industries such as medical devices, aerospace, automotive, and nuclear industries.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Feng Lin: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **Zhou Su:** Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Mubasher Ali:** Resources, Project administration. **Yuanfu Tan:** Software, Investigation. **Wei-Hsin Liao:** Investigation, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Hay Wong:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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